

Electrolysis of Strong Acids and Strong Alkalis with Special Reference to Their Non-Faradaic Behaviour*

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When a solution of a strong acid is electrolysed with bright platinum electrodes, the current gradually falls with time but attains a limiting value (nearly 1 mA at 230 volt) after a certain time. On electrolysis at this current strength, solutions of a strong acid upto the concentration of 10^{-3} N exhibit non-Faradaic features with strong overall deficit in the liberation of gaseous products and cathodic preference; as the concentration is increased to 10^{-2} N, a strong acid exhibits more or less Faradaic electrolysis. A solution of a strong alkali on electrolysis behaves similar to that of a strong acid of comparable strength. Electrolysis of a system having 10^{-3} N acid at the anode and 10^{-3} N alkali at the cathode is highly non-Faradaic whereas the system containing 10^{-3} N acid at anode or 10^{-3} N alkali at cathode and water at the other electrode is completely Faradaic. This at least indicates that conditions at both electrodes must be mutually conducive to give rise to the phenomenon of non-Faradaic electrolysis.

NON-FARADAIC features manifested in the electrolysis of practically all aqueous salt solutions under certain conditions (low electrolyte concentration and/or low current density)¹ prompted us to study the electrolysis of strong acids and strong alkalis and we report our findings on the same in this communication.

Experimental

The experimental arrangement of the cells and the method of analysis of the liberated gases are the same as described earlier². Bright platinum foils (1 cm^2) have been used as electrodes. The acid and alkali solutions are prepared by appropriate dilution with double distilled water of the concentrated volumetric solutions supplied by B. D. H. Sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric, chromic and perchloric acids have been selected for the study. Sodium hydroxide is selected as a representative member of strong alkali.

Results and Discussion

The study of electrolysis of strong acids and strong alkalis is beset with the experimental difficulty due to the migration of strong acids and alkalis to the anode and cathode, respectively, causing a fall of current if the voltage is maintained constant. However, it is found that dilute solutions of strong acids and alkalis are amenable to study, provided the applied voltage is nearly 230 volt. A typical current-time curve for 10^{-3} N sulphuric acid is depicted in Fig. 1. This limiting value of the current ($\sim 1 \text{ mA}$) is higher than what would be expected if water was to be formed in the cathode region. The reason for this steady current during

Fig. 1. Current-time curve for electrolysis of 10^{-3} N sulphuric acid.

electrolysis of an acid solution is that a very small portion of the acid always remains in the cathode chamber particularly if the original solution is very dilute and the current is low (of the order of 1 mA). In fact, the current remains fairly steady even on continuous electrolysis for weeks when more than a few tens of times the current equivalent of the total acid present must have passed. The behaviour of current remaining steady during electrolysis of a weak acid (as acetic acid) has also been attributed to a steady state concentration differential attained after an initial period of electrolysis³. The attainment of this steady state concentration differential has recently been ascribed to the reverse migration of ions caused by the accumulation of some electrostatic charge, positive for the anolyte and negative for the catholyte, during electrolysis⁴.

The general features (Faradaic or non-Faradaic) exhibited in the electrolysis of the systems mentioned

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above are tabulated in Table 1. All the acids studied, except HCl, give more or less similar results; with 10^{-2} N HCl, though not with 10^{-3} N, chlorine is liberated at the anode. A solution of strong alkali when subjected to electrolysis behaves similar to the strong acid of comparable strength.

TABLE 1—FARADAIC OR NON-FARADAIC NATURE IN THE ELECTROLYSIS OF DIFFERENT ACID-ALKALI SYSTEMS

Catholyte	Anolyte	Nature of Electrolysis
10^{-2} N acid in both anode and cathode		Non-Faradaic with (i) strong deficit, (ii) high cathode preference and (iii) co-liberation
10^{-2} N acid in both anode and cathode		More or less Faradaic
Dilute alkali in both anode and cathode		Similar to that of acid of comparable strength
Water	10^{-2} N acid	Non-Faradaic
Water	10^{-3} N acid	Tends to be Faradaic
Alkali ($<10^{-2}$ N)	Water	Non-Faradaic
Alkali ($>10^{-2}$ N)	Water	Faradaic
10^{-2} N alkali	10^{-2} N acid	Highly non-Faradaic
10^{-3} N alkali	10^{-3} N acid	Non-Faradaic to a small extent
10^{-1} N alkali	10^{-1} N acid	Faradaic
10^{-2} N alkali	10^{-2} N acid	Faradaic
10^{-3} N alkali	10^{-3} N acid	Faradaic

The results of electrolysis of the systems having acid at cathode and alkali at anode are very interesting. As the electrolysis of such a system having 10^{-2} N concentration at both electrodes begins, the alkali as well as the acid solution starts moving towards the respective counter electrodes and on prolonged electrolysis for several hours, the cathode and the anode compartments become completely alkaline and acidic, respectively. As a result, co-liberation is not noticeable at the beginning of electrolysis, but becomes prominent in the later part of the electrolysis. Low concentration ($\sim 10^{-3}$ N) of the acid

and alkali at the two electrodes gives rise to non-Faradaic results from the very beginning of electrolysis since the acid and alkali requires only a very short time to migrate to the counter electrodes.

No suitable mechanism² has been put forward as yet to explain all the features of non-Faradaic electrolysis. Whatever the mechanism may be, a remarkable point to emerge from the present study is that though a system of a 10^{-2} N solution of acid or alkali in both the anode and cathode as well as the system of 10^{-2} N acid at the anode or 10^{-2} N alkali at cathode and water at the other electrode exhibits Faradaic electrolysis, a system of 10^{-2} N acid at the anode and 10^{-2} N alkali at the cathode exhibits non-Faradaic results. This at least indicates that what we have termed non-Faradaic behaviour must be a kind of co-operative phenomenon where the conditions at both the electrodes must be mutually conducive to the process.

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